

A Comparative Risk Analysis of Fuel Cell and Electrolyzer Failure Modes

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Abstract—A widespread rollout of hydrogen technologies depends on ensuring operational safety, which must be established by accounting for the unique characteristics of hydrogen systems and hydrogen’s physical and chemical properties. In this context, this work examines safety-relevant failure risks across solid oxide electrolyzers, solid oxide fuel cells, proton exchange membrane electrolyzers, and proton exchange membrane fuel cells. These systems were selected for a comparative assessment using the Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA), highlighting technology-specific failure modes and associated effects. This comparative FMEA identifies common failure modes and their effects across technologies and informs suitable safety strategies. The approach is grounded in information from real-world applications and is structured around process flow diagrams of the main subsystems, resulting in a flexible tool for failure analysis. Overall, the study supports safer deployment of the hydrogen value chain by linking identified failure modes to mitigation strategies.

Index Terms—Hydrogen, safety, FMEA, electrolyzer, fuel cell, failure mode.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hydrogen has been a crucial element in process industries for decades, serving as a key component in various chemical processes. Today, stakeholders are investing in further promoting H₂, leveraging its proven potential as an energy vector [1]. In addition, the growing interest in H₂ technologies stems from their potential for sustainability and effective integration with electrification solutions. Various examples exist today, ranging from fuel cell cars and liquid H₂ ferries to early-stage solutions for the aviation sector. However, two relevant barriers still inhibit the widespread implementation of H₂-based solutions. First, the still limited and costly H₂ production burdens the economic competitiveness of such solutions, especially when compared with

conventional and widely accepted technologies, which can rely on a fully developed value chain [2]. Scalability is the second crucial barrier hindering the rollout of H₂-based systems in the energy sector: the limited operational experience and considerable costs, coupled with persistent knowledge gaps, negatively impact the swift development of the H₂ value chain, influencing production, storage, transportation, and final utilization [3]. In this light, the current paper explores some key H₂ technologies and their potential safety concerns. In particular, two H₂ production systems and two H₂ utilization systems are addressed through the Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA). The FMEA is an effective tool widely accepted and implemented in the process industry for identifying relevant hazards and associated failures. It is often used as an early-stage risk analysis solution [4], [5]. The qualitative nature of the FMEA enables the investigation and assessment of failure modes affecting, for example, process plants and industrial units, providing a compromise between risk assessment capabilities and in-depth information requirements. In this light, a Solid Oxide Electrolyzer (SOEL) [6], a Proton Exchange Membrane Electrolyzer (PEMEL) [7], a Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) [8], and a Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell (PEMFC) [9] are selected for a comparative FMEA assessment. More specifically, process flow diagrams (PFDs) are used for each of these four technologies, enabling identification of the dominant hazards in their main subsystems. The scope of the current work is therefore to provide the reader with actionable insights, based on the specific characteristics of each H₂-based solution for safety-aware design purposes, without necessitating a thorough quantitative risk assessment. This choice reflects a simple argument: the technologies mentioned

above are often compared in terms of suitability for specific solutions (i.e., mobile vs. fixed), effectiveness, involved temperatures and pressures, material requirements, and more; however, comparative safety analyses seem to remain scarce. Works aimed at developing comparative risk assessments for H₂ technologies have been conducted. Still, they are primarily focused on the overall value chain, as seen in the case of the energy chain for both H₂-based and fossil-based technologies [10]. Similarly, KPI-based evaluations compare PEMFC with LNG-powered systems [11] and literature reviews describe the role of computational fluid dynamics in consequence assessment using a comparative framework [12]. In addition, a hazard and operability analysis (HazOp) was proposed for H₂O electrolysis plants [13]. In this context, the comparative safety analysis proposed in the current work represents a novel attempt to support H₂O-based solutions.

Sec. II provides a detailed description of the adopted FMEA approach, along with definitions of the systems and subsystems for each PFD. Sec. III provides a comparative description of the main characteristics of the four systems addressed, highlights the main findings, and discusses the results. Finally, the main conclusions of this work are presented in Sec. IV.

II. METHODOLOGY

The PFD-based FMEA approach adopted in this work is a flexible and effective tool for achieving a structured comparative overview of the SOEL, PEMEL, SOFC, and PEMFC. The FMEA framework is used to evaluate potential failure modes and their associated effects, which serve as inputs for probability and consequence evaluations [4], [5]. Additionally, key failure modes are evaluated in the FMEA to support the definition of ad hoc hazard mitigation measures. These can be categorized into preventive measures that reduce the likelihood of an unwanted event, reactive measures that mitigate its consequences, and safe-by-design solutions that improve the design of the systems under assessment. The suggestion of such measures is the primary focus of this analysis, grounded in the design of existing H₂ technologies. Specifically, the four systems involved are analyzed as part of the Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) framework, which aims to improve safety, performance, and environmental impact across the entire life cycle [14]. As such, the analyzed products are currently available on the market, and the proposed FMEA result is the outcome of workshops with technology providers and operators,

corroborated by information from the literature and research experience. The adoption of PFDs, rather than Piping and Instrumentation Diagrams (P&ID), reflects a product-agnostic approach that focuses on the main processes and subsystems, allowing for the identification and comparison of failure modes and for performing a comparative assessment without a detailed risk analysis.

The adopted method excludes semi-quantitative and quantitative criteria, whose definition would corroborate the obtained results. These were excluded to prioritize the identification of key failure modes.

A. Process Flow Diagrams

Fig. 1 shows the PFDs adopted for the electrolyzer configurations, differentiating between SO and PEM technologies. In the case of the SOEL (see Fig. 1a), the steam is directly used in the stack to produce H₂, while O₂ (mixed with H₂O) is a by-product for the case of the PEMEL (see Fig. 1b). The SOEL presents an additional H₂ source, typically used during start-up to promote effective electrolysis at the stack, and a *recycled H₂* bypass, which can be used to ensure a sufficient H₂ inlet at the cathode without relying on an external H₂ source. A condenser can be included to remove remaining H₂O at the outlet. In the PEMEL case, H₂ is produced at considerable pressure, and a high-pressure separator, which can be followed by a lower-pressure separator, is needed to ensure target purity at the outlet. In the SOEL case, H₂O is typically removed from the system through condensers and discharged (indicated with *vent*). On the other hand, the PEMEL uses liquid distilled H₂O as its primary input, relying on a recirculation system to ensure correct H₂O management upstream of the pump. The air circuit (SOEL case) provides O₂ to the anode before exiting the system. Given the higher temperature required by this technology, a recuperator box is used to warm the air and the inlet H₂, thereby maximizing efficiency. The cooling system for electrolyzers is not discussed and is considered an external system, excluded from the analysis. The FMEA analysis is built on these subsystems, analyzing the elements in each circuit and their potential failure modes and effects.

The same approach adopted for the electrolyzers is proposed for the fuel cells. In this case, emphasis is also placed on the cooling system, which is typically a closed system (especially in mobile applications) and is key to ensuring operability and functionality. Fig. 2 shows the PFDs adopted for the SOFC and

Fig. 1. PFDs of a SOEL and a PEMEL. The colors indicate different subsystems: steam and O₂ lines in orange and red, respectively; the produced/used H₂ in purple; the H₂O line in blue; the air circuit in black; the external cooling system in green.

the PEMFC, highlighting the various subsystems. The H₂ circuit is characterized by recirculation in both systems. The SOFC utilizes the recycled H₂ upstream of the recuperator box, and a correct inlet pressure must be maintained for proper H₂ recirculation (see Fig. 2a). Similarly, the PEMFC system recirculates H₂ to recycle the non-reacted fraction downstream of the cathode, aiming at increasing the H₂ conversion (see Fig. 2b). The air circuit is used to provide O₂ at the cathode (in the SOFC) and to the anode (in the PEMFC). A recuperator box is again present in the SO configuration, and an additional condenser can be included to recover the discharged heat using the coolant loop. This closed loop ensures a correct temperature for the recirculating H₂ upstream of the recuperator box, which preheats the fuel at the anode inlet. In the PEMFC configuration, the air circuit can present two (or more) inlets, used to provide air to the anode and again recuperate heat through an air-air heat exchanger. For mobile applications, one of the inlet air can be achieved through direct air intake, supported by a compressor in some cases. The closed coolant circuit provides refrigeration for the fuel cell stack (low-temperature fuel cells) and can also be used to further regulate the inlet air temperature.

B. Failure Mode and Effects Analysis

The following provides a brief overview of the adopted FMEA workflow [4], [5].

1) *Identify subsystems*: This step involves analyzing the PFDs and identifying the various subsystems (as described in Sec. II-A).

2) *Identify key components inside each subsystem*: In this phase, critical components are discussed, distinguishing between multi-subsystem components and

those unique to each subsystem (e.g., the separator in the PEMEL shown in Fig. 1 is relevant to both the O₂ and H₂O subsystems).

3) *List plausible failure modes*: This phase leads to the identification of most of the failure modes that can affect the systems in question.

4) *Determine effects at subsystem and system level*: Based on the outcome of the previous phase and operational experience, the failure effects are determined, highlighting multi-system effects and possible joint failure mechanisms (i.e., if the SOEL separator fails to remove impurities and/or steam condenses in cold spots, it can affect the recuperator box, thus posing safety concerns for the H₂ circuit as well).

5) *Identify causes and current controls*: Possible failure causes and available control systems are discussed to assess the key functionalities of monitoring systems and the safety barriers that may be installed. For example, suppose the coolant pump in the PEMFC configuration fails due to inadequate maintenance or incorrect design/sizing. In that case, a temperature check at the fuel cell stack should detect the abnormal temperature rise, alert the user/operator, and trigger a safety shutdown.

C. Systems Specifications

This section addresses the key differences in design, materials, operating conditions, and efficiency that characterize SO and PEM solutions. Tab. I reviews the key differences between the four configurations.

SO devices rely on a dense ceramic electrolyte, typically yttria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ), which conducts O²⁻ ions at temperatures between 650 °C – 900 °C [6]. The fuel-side electrode is commonly a Ni-YSZ cermet. In contrast, the air-side electrode is based on perovskite

Fig. 2. PFDs of a SOFC and a PEMFC. The colors indicate different subsystems: the produced/used H_2 in purple; the air (and H_2O produced from the stack) circuit in black; the cooling system in green.

TABLE I
CLASSIFICATION OF ELECTROLYZER AND FUEL CELL
TECHNOLOGIES

Technology Type	Electrolyzer Electricity $\rightarrow H_2$	Fuel Cell $H_2 \rightarrow$ Electricity
SO (high temp.)	SOEL	SOFC
PEM (low temp.)	PEMEL	PEMFC

materials and other materials that define the thermal, mechanical, and chemical limits of SOEL/SOFC operation. On the other hand, PEM devices utilize a proton-conducting polymer membrane (e.g., Nafion) [7]. Catalysts are based on platinum-group metals supported on carbon or titanium, depending on the application, which typically contribute to the generally higher costs of these solutions. Flow-field plates can be graphite-based for fuel cells and Ti-based for electrolyzers, both of which resist corrosion in high-potential environments. Operation at $50^\circ C - 90^\circ C$ simplifies thermal management (low temperature applications) but requires tight control of membrane hydration, gas purity, and H_2O recycling. Tab. II collects these key characteristics, displaying the main specifications of these four configurations. SO systems are characterized by higher efficiency, which can be achieved at high temperatures (thermally activated regime), ensuring ionic conductivity for internal reforming (SOFC) and efficient steam electrolysis (SOEL). Key control variables include temperature uniformity, fuel utilization ratio, differential pressure between air and fuel manifolds, and gas composition. Thermal gradients can lead to electrolyte cracking, while excessive fuel starvation or redox cycling can degrade the Ni-based anode.

PEM systems, in contrast, operate in a kinetically dominated regime where membrane hydration, catalyst poisoning, and H_2O management determine performance and durability. Critical variables include membrane hydration, gas purity (especially CO , SO_2 , and metal-ion contaminants), system pressure, and H_2O management. PEM electrolyzers achieve higher efficiency at elevated pressures but may experience increased mechanical stress on the membrane. Fuel cells must prevent both membrane dry-out and flooding to ensure stable operation. Regarding energy management, SO solutions typically achieve higher thermodynamic efficiency due to their greater operating temperatures, the inclusion of recuperator boxes, and the ability to integrate waste heat. PEM devices typically show slightly lower energy efficiency, but excel in transient response, partial-load operation, and compact design.

The high-level comparison carried out in these sections highlights the following key characteristics:

- SOEL excels in efficiency and relative tolerance to specific impurities, while PEMEL offers fast dynamics and compact design;
- SOFC systems provide high efficiency and fuel flexibility, whereas PEMFCs are more suitable for transportation and rapid-load applications;
- Electrolyzers prioritize gas purity, pressure control, and catalyst protection; fuel cells prioritize heat rejection, H_2O balance, and contamination control;
- SO systems are limited by high-temperature materials constraints, whereas PEM systems are limited by chemical stability and membrane hydration.

Such key characteristics have been studied and optimized throughout the last decades, leading to the development of ready-to-use products for the market.

TABLE II
TYPICAL OPERATING CONDITIONS FOR SOEL, SOFC, PEMEL, AND PEMFC SYSTEMS

Parameter	SOEL [15]	SOFC [16]	PEMEL [17]	PEMFC [18]
Temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]	650 – 850	700 – 900	50 – 80	50 – 90
Pressure [bar]	1 – 30	1 – 3	up to 30 – 40	1 – 3
Main reactant	$\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{g})$	H_2	$\text{H}_2\text{O}(\text{l})$	H_2
Charge carrier	O^{2-}	O^{2-}	H^+	H^+
Startup behavior	Slow	Slow	Fast	Fast
Gas purity sensitivity	Low–moderate	Moderate	Very high	Very high
Energy efficiency	80 – 90% (HHV)	60 – 75% (HHV)	50 – 65% el. (90% CHP)	40 – 60%

TABLE III
SUMMARY OF KEY COMPONENTS AND CRITICAL FAILURE MODES ACROSS SOEL, PEMEL, SOFC, AND PEMFC SYSTEMS

	SOEL	PEMFC
SOFC	Recuperator boxes <i>Cross-leak (exchanger failure)</i>	Recirculation systems <i>Improper H_2 recirculation</i>
PEMEL	Separators <i>Incorrect fuel feed</i>	Fuel line <i>Fail to feed high-purity fuel</i>

Note: Key components and failure modes are shown in **bold** and *italics*, respectively.

III. RESULTS

Tab. III summarizes the key aspects of the comparative assessment, highlighting the critical components and failure modes shared by the four architectures. The remainder of the section gives a comparative overview and related discussion. It is worth noting that while the hazards, failure modes, and effects were identified through FMEA sessions between researchers and technology providers for specific configurations, the following findings should be considered general key concepts for each system, rather than addressed to a particular marketed product.

A. FMEA Insights for SOEL

The following is a collection of the key failure modes identified for the SOEL system, discussing their effects, mitigation strategies, and detection systems.

1) *H_2 Recirculation Failure*: The H_2 recirculation system is key to optimal SOEL functioning; it is, in fact, installed to ensure that a defined H_2 fraction is available at the stack inlet (typically around 1%), which is required for correct operation and target conversion

efficiency. A lack of H_2 at the inlet, caused by a recirculation failure, can degrade the stack, leading to unexpected performance loss. This failure can also be initiated by incorrect start-up practices, which are critical for SO configurations in general, and optimal coordination between the recycling system and the additional H_2 source is necessary to mitigate the consequences of this event (i.e., if the additional H_2 source is available during recirculation failure, it can act as a back-up). The inclusion of H_2 recirculation blowers is suggested as an effective preventive measure, along with thermodynamic simulation during the design stage, mass flow sensors, and differential pressure sensors.

2) *Cross-Leak in Recuperator Box*: The recuperator box ensures that both H_2 and air reach the stack at a target temperature for suitable operation. A malfunction of the H_2 heat exchanger can be caused by impurities or liquid H_2O in the steam line, potentially resulting from an upstream failure at the separator, which can lead to corrosion and cracking in the recuperator box. This event can result in a H_2 and steam leak in the recuperator box and the surrounding environment, potentially generating explosive mixtures and jet fires, especially given the elevated temperatures involved. Therefore, this event may be considered critical to the safety of operators in the surrounding area and should be detected at an early stage through mass flow monitoring and maintenance to prevent corrosion.

3) *Stack Cross-Flow*: Cross-flow at the stack is typically a severe failure mode relevant to electrolyzers in general. It can lead to the formation of H_2/O_2 explosive mixtures and result in auto-ignition, especially given the typical high temperatures involved in SOEL operation. This event may occur in connection with fractures in the SO electrolyte, loss of seal integrity, mechanical distortion, and wear. If cross-flow occurs, the generated gas mixture can ignite within the cell, causing localized cracking that can spread to neighboring cells and

trigger catastrophic stack failures. The leading causes of cross-leak include rapid thermal cycling, excessive differential pressure between the H_2 and the air side, or degradation of ceramic seals. Detection is critical and relies on O_2 sensors installed at the H_2 outlet and/or on stack-temperature mapping to identify hotspots. Additionally, monitoring pressure differentials across the electrolyte is also crucial. Prevention encompasses controlled start-up procedures (slow thermal ramp rates) and good control over mechanical stress during operation.

B. FMEA Insights for PEMEL

The analysis of the PEMEL identified two criticalities for the H_2O circuit and one for the H_2 circuit.

1) *Lack of Liquid at the Stack*: A lack of liquid at the stack can be caused by a pump malfunction, leading to a loss of pressure at the H_2O electrode (anode). In fact, the anodic pump ensures liquid circulation at the anode; its absence may lead to membrane overheating, followed by sudden degradation and the potential formation of explosive H_2/O_2 mixtures. This event may be attributed to a mechanical seal leak, which may explain the lack of H_2O , as well as power supply instability at the pump and mechanical wear. In any case, the main failure mode is attributable to the pump malfunction, which can be detected through redundant monitoring systems, such as temperature controls coupled with pressure sensors and emergency shutdown systems. The chances of the event can be reduced by installing high-reliability pumps.

2) *Overpressure Burst at the Stack*: An additional failure mode is an overpressure event, again caused by an anodic pump malfunction. This results in a pressure buildup in the stack, which can lead to membrane rupture and fluid crossover, ultimately forming explosive H_2/O_2 mixtures. Potential causes range from mechanical seal issues to power supply instability, with periodic maintenance activities and adoption of a high-quality pump as the primary prevention strategies. The suggested detection system is a redundant pressure transmitter, identified as suitable for both failure modes above, which should maximize detection capabilities and ensure effective risk management.

3) *Excessive Thermal Stress at H_2/H_2O Separator*: Concerning the H_2 circuit, one relevant failure mode was identified for the H_2/H_2O separator. The function of this separator is to ensure effective removal of residual H_2O from the H_2 stream, which can be achieved using multiple separators at different pressure levels as shown

in Fig. 1b. A loss of temperature control is considered a critical failure mode for this component, as it promotes overheating and ultimately leads to thermal stress and material degradation, thereby reducing the quality of the produced H_2 stream by increasing its H_2O content. The leading causes may be attributed to a failure of the regeneration cycle (i.e., the H_2O recirculation circuit) or a failure of the de-oxidizer (not shown in Fig. 1b, typically positioned after the cooling system on the H_2 side), which may induce excessive temperatures in the H_2 stream and overheating at the H_2/H_2O separator. Preventive measures should include good monitoring of the regeneration cycle itself, effective maintenance, and the adoption of a heat-resistant adsorbent, with an overheating-based shutdown system that automatically activates at temperatures exceeding $200^\circ C$. This is considered a critical failure mode due to the potential to generate explosive mixtures and release them into the environment. A comprehensive assessment should be conducted to account for the de-oxidizer's failure modes that are currently not included in this analysis.

C. FMEA Insights for SOFC

The identified failure modes for fuel cell applications consider the different operating conditions and variables, with respect to electrolyzers, as well as the typical application characteristics. Regarding the SOFC configuration, the key failure modes and their effects are discussed below.

1) *Excessive Mass Flow Rate at Fuel Recirculation System*: The H_2 recirculation system is key to the good functioning of an SOFC. It is implemented to ensure a defined composition, pressure, mass flow, and temperature at the fuel cell stack, as well as to avoid H_2 losses. A failure of this system can cause excessive mass flow to the fuel cell module, resulting from incorrect design and sizing, and may lead to cross-flow at the fuel cell stack, promoting the formation of explosive mixtures. The inclusion of a proper recirculation blower is suggested as a preventive measure, along with thermodynamic simulation at the design stage, and detection systems (mass flow and pressure sensors).

2) *Hot Air Leakage*: On the opposite side of the stack, a failure mode is identified due to insufficient air mass flow caused by the air blower's failure. This failure can result in both a loss of mass flow and insufficient temperature at the cathode, degrading conversion efficiency and causing a pressure drop at the cathode, potentially inducing cross-flow. Moreover,

mass flow loss can be due to an air leak in the environment, which alone poses a hazard to operators and nearby equipment.

3) *Cold Air Inlet*: In case of a failure of the air heater (not included in Fig. 2a, upstream of the recuperator box), air can be fed to the stack at low temperatures, which can promote a variety of failure effects, including a loss of electrical output, the degradation of the electrolyte, and damage to the overall stack. Optimal design and selection of ad hoc components are key to ensuring an air inlet at a sufficient temperature, along with temperature monitoring systems and emergency shutdown controllers.

D. FMEA Insights for PEMFC

The analysis of the PEMFC configuration identified its main criticalities, which relate to the H₂ supply system and the stack and are summarized as follows.

1) *External Leak*: The H₂ supply system ensures that sufficient H₂ is continuously fed to the stack, with a mass flow rate that depends on the power required for efficient operation. The failure of this subsystem can lead to fuel loss at the stack and a generalized H₂ shortage (i.e., H₂ starvation, discussed below), which may, in turn, cause membrane rupture, generate local hotspots, and trigger sudden cell failure. An external leak can also pose a fire hazard, potentially generating H₂ jet fires from pinhole leaks. This type of event can be initiated by mechanical vibrations and fatigue, particularly promoted by H₂-enhanced fatigue in various alloys, and can be detected through H₂ sensors, variations in the mass flow, and pressure drops [19]. The occurrence of events can be effectively limited by adopting proper seal fittings, conducting leak-tightness tests, and using H₂-resistant materials, as stainless steel.

2) *Leak Towards Cathode Outlet / Coolant Circuit*: In the event of a leak, H₂ can contaminate both the cathode outlet and the coolant circuit, potentially posing a fire hazard by forming explosive mixtures with air, while also negatively affecting stack performance. This hazard may be initiated by a variety of causes, ranging from corrosion mechanisms within the materials implemented at the stack itself and in the coolant circuit, in combination with H₂ embrittlement and/or mechanical fatigue. Additionally, defective components, improper design, and off-design temperature conditions can contribute to H₂ starvation. Therefore, a key preventive barrier against such a failure mode may result in proper material selection and sizing, considering fatigue life

in H₂ environments and corrosion allowance. In fact, this event may be initiated by pinhole corrosion in metallic materials, which is not easily detectable at early stages. However, good pressure monitoring and H₂ sensors installed in both the coolant and air circuits, downstream of the stack, could be used to initiate safety shutdowns in case of leakage, along with loss of fuel alarms that variations in stack power output can trigger.

3) *H₂ Starvation*: H₂ starvation was mentioned as a failure mode above, and it is indeed a typical concern for PEMFC configurations. H₂ starvation can be defined as an insufficient H₂ supply to the fuel cell (it can occur locally at individual cells or generalized to the entire stack). The causes of H₂ starvation include potential malfunction of the H₂ supply subsystem (such as valves and pressure regulators), and may also be triggered by insufficient/ineffective purging. Moreover, the presence of impurities and particulates in the H₂ stream is hugely relevant for localized H₂ starvation, which can generate hotspots, voltage reversal in individual cells, membrane degradation, and ultimately rupture. Optimal control over individual cell voltage can effectively detect H₂ starvation, which may also be supported by temperature mapping and feedback from the purging procedures. Good design practices and material choice are key to preventing starvation. However, the most relevant preventive solution is the use of pure H₂, a characteristic and limitation of PEMFC technology, thereby reducing the risk posed by impurities, particulates, and other contaminants in the fuel cell.

4) *Anodic Recirculation Failure*: The H₂ recirculation system ensures that residual H₂ at the anode outlet is correctly recycled to achieve optimal fuel consumption and increase efficiency. Various PEMFC configurations may include specific components in the recirculation line, including a H₂ blower and check valves, as well as pressure regulators and filters. Mechanical blower failures and wear, clogged filters, valve malfunctions, or incorrect pressure regulation could trigger a recirculation system failure. In such cases, the final result could be higher fuel consumption, as the residual H₂ would only be vented to the exhaust, negatively impacting the overall energy efficiency of the PEMFC stack. If no control over the supply fuel management system is installed, this failure can even cause H₂ starvation at the stack, potentially resulting in the events discussed previously. Overall, the anode control system should detect anodic recirculation failure to ensure correct fuel flow at the stack inlet. This

should be monitored using flow sensors downstream of the recirculation unit, as well as differential pressure measurements at both the anode and cathode sides. High-performance blowers should also be installed to reduce the likelihood of the event, along with adequate maintenance and the use of filters or valve bypasses.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

This work conducted a qualitative safety assessment of SOEL, PEMEL, SOFC, and PEMFC by comparing FMEA results. The systems were described in dedicated PFDs, which identified the main subsystems and key components. The analysis identified key failure modes for each system, highlighting similarities and differences. (i) SOEL & PEMEL share relevant failure modes involving the steam and the H₂ separators, respectively. While such systems differ in operation, effective separation control is vital for both types to remove impurities and ensure proper fuel feeding. (ii) While operating at different conditions, both SOFC & PEMFC rely on H₂ circulation systems that ensure correct stack operation. The reliable functioning of these systems is therefore crucial to mitigating the identified hazards in both configurations, including H₂ starvation and cross-flow. (iii) SOEL & SOFC show criticalities in terms of the temperatures involved. In fact, recuperator boxes are often used to ensure heat recovery, but potential hazards related to heat exchanger degradation, corrosion, and leaks should be further investigated and their occurrence mitigated through the prevention strategies discussed above. (iv) PEMEL & PEMFC show considerable sensitivity to fuel purity. Therefore, their safety depends on the reliable operation of the components upstream of the stack (i.e., the anodic pump and recirculation system), which prevents impurities from triggering critical failure, including H₂ starvation and membrane overheating.

Future works will focus on an analysis based on semi-quantitative KPIs (e.g., *risk priority numbers*) to allow for a systematic comparison and risk ranking among products.

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